

17 March 2020

To: OpenScience@ostp.eop.gov

Subject: RFC Response: Desirable Repository Characteristics

Thank you for the opportunity to comment on the “**Desirable Characteristics of Repositories for Managing and Sharing Data Resulting From Federally Funded Research**”. We are affiliated with the American Geophysical Union (AGU), a society representing the international Earth and space science community. The AGU community, along with a broad number of stakeholders, has been working on changes in practices and policies requiring published research to have supporting data and software made available through an appropriate repository, preferably a domain-specific repository when available while also recognizing the importance of general and institutional repositories. This work is building on the **Enabling FAIR Data [1]** project, funded by Arnold Ventures and subsequent work by the National Science Foundation, that established a Commitment Statement [2] as well as Author Guidelines [3] adopted by most of the major publishers. This effort advocates a change in scientific culture towards data sharing and making data open and FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) [4]. AGU has also recently updated its Data Position Statement [5] affirming the importance of repositories for preserving scientific data and other relevant evidence and the need to follow leading practices...to ensure data is “**processed, shared, and used ethically, and is available, preserved, documented, and fairly credited.**”

The repository community has a significant role in the success of the goals defined in the Enabling FAIR Data project. The list of desired characteristics for scientific repositories in the Draft is important and aligns well with the work we are doing with AGU and our community. There are additional topics that should be included in the list:

1. **Linking of research products:** Research efforts create digital research products including publications, data, software, and more. Few platforms support all possible formats, and commonly, different repositories are required for proper management and preservation even within single projects. These products need to be linked through persistent identifiers, grant ID’s, and researcher ID’s (e.g. ORCID). This would allow for robust discovery and transparency. Search platforms need to be trained to find and index different types of products especially if they have a persistent identifier.
2. **Confidential access to datasets during publication peer review:** In order to evaluate research, peer reviewers need access to data. Repositories make this possible by either publishing the data prior to the paper being published, by providing a temporary “share link”, or by providing secure “embargoed” access to reviewers only. As the publishing community more closely integrates with scientific repositories, this support to publication peer review is necessary. Single-blind and double-blind peer review requires this access to be confidential. Further, once the journal

publication related to a dataset is publicly available, publication of the dataset should be linked and/or triggered automatically. At this time this process is manually coordinated (at best).

3. **Software as context for data.** We learn more about research data by looking at the related software (e.g. code, workflow, models). Software sharing is necessary to better understand the data and the associated research. Repositories that support software preservation are important along with relevant links to related data and publication.
4. **Clear licensing to support data and software reuse:** Researchers who seek data or software for use in new research need to understand the usage license. There are different leading practices for software and data research products.
5. **Versioning and provenance:** Data analyses associated with a research grant commonly require existing datasets to be reprocessed and/or integrated with other datasets. The process of preparing data for this integration and possible transformation into more useful formats results in valuable derived data products that can be of significance to the broader community. Versioning also occurs when data is reprocessed to create better versions of a dataset as issues are found, or new understanding emerges. Establishing links from original datasets to derived data products is important to be able to unambiguously track the full provenance and possible reuse of existing datasets in new research. Full provenance is also important as it enables the original funders, researchers and institutions that enabled the creation of any source dataset to have identity and attribution.
6. **Funding and archive support for domain repositories:** Many domain repositories originate from a need by the community and tend to be funded with grants having time frames of 2-3 years. This short time frame limits long-term planning and the ability to evolve capabilities to meet desired characteristics like those listed in this draft. Adequate funding allows for incorporating needs from researchers and provides data products that are easier to discover and use. Making government-funded archives available to these domain repositories provides long-term preservation for data that are part of the scientific record, protecting them from loss of funding. This is one of the most significant and important challenges [4]. Leading repositories should have long-term support such that researchers and publishers will be confident that data supporting peer-reviewed research will be available. When policy recommends a future date to purge data, the data landing page with descriptive metadata will be maintained to identify that the data existed information about the data.
7. **Machine readable and actionable:** As required by the FAIR Data Principles [6], repositories need to provide both human and machine capable methods for discovery, access, and action. Researchers will benefit from using tools to help locate relevant data. Machine ability to read and take action will enable efficiencies for researchers, thereby allowing more time for analysis.

In addition to the specific desirable characteristics indicated above, societies such as AGU and the broader publishing community have been collaborating with scientific repositories to define and develop

leading practices. We hope that these draft guidelines recognize and complement this effort and that as leading practices continue to develop are sufficiently adaptable.

Thank you again for the opportunity to provide comments.

Best regards,

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[1] <https://copdess.org/enabling-fair-data-project/>

[2] <https://copdess.org/enabling-fair-data-project/commitment-statement-in-the-earth-space-and-environmental-sciences/>

[3] <https://copdess.org/enabling-fair-data-project/author-guidelines/>

[4] Stall, S, et al. (2019), Make scientific data FAIR, *Nature* **570**, 27-29 (2019) doi: [10.1038/d41586-019-01720-7](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-019-01720-7)

[5] https://www.agu.org/Share-and-Advocate/Share/Polycymakers/Position-Statements/Position_Data

[6] Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* **3**, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>